

UCI datasets selected for experiments

Original UCI name	name	#tasks	#instances	#inputs
<u>3D Road Network (North Jutland, Denmark)</u>	3Droad	1	434874	3
<u>Air Quality</u>	airquality	5	9357	8
<u>Airfoil Self-Noise</u>	airfoil	1	1503	5
<u>Appliances energy prediction</u>	appliances	1	19735	27
<u>Auto MPG</u>	autompg	1	392	7
<u>Automobile</u>	automobile	1	159	13
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Aotizhongxin	6	31815	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Changping	6	32681	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Dingling	6	31306	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Dongsi	6	30338	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Guanyuan	6	32263	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Gucheng	6	32504	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Huairou	6	31708	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Nongzhanguan	6	33114	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Shunyi	6	30194	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Tiantan	6	32843	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Wanliu	6	30634	5
<u>Beijing Multi-Site Air-Quality Data</u>	PRSA_Wanshouxigong	6	32768	5
<u>Beijing PM2.5 Data</u>	beijing_pm25	1	41757	6
<u>Bias correction of numerical prediction model temperature forecast</u>	bias	2	7588	21
<u>Bike Sharing Dataset</u>	bike_day	1	731	6
<u>Bike Sharing Dataset</u>	bike_hour	1	17379	6
<u>BlogFeedback</u>	blogfeedback	1	52397	11
<u>Buzz in social media</u>	TomsHardware	1	28179	96
<u>Buzz in social media</u>	Twitter	1	583250	71
<u>Combined Cycle Power Plant</u>	ccpp	1	9568	4
<u>Communities and Crime</u>	communities	1	1994	122
<u>Communities and Crime Unnormalized</u>	comm_unnorm	1	2215	124
<u>Computer Hardware</u>	machine	1	209	6
<u>Concrete Compressive Strength</u>	concrete	1	1030	8
<u>Concrete Slump Test</u>	slump	3	104	7
<u>Condition Based Maintenance of Naval Propulsion Plants</u>	CBM	1	11934	16
<u>CSM (Conventional and Social Media Movies) Dataset 2014 and 2015</u>	CSM	1	231	9
<u>Daily Demand Forecasting Orders</u>	dailydemand	1	60	12
<u>Electrical Grid Stability Simulated Data</u>	elect_grid	1	10000	13

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<u>Energy efficiency</u>	energy_efficiency	2	768	7
<u>Facebook Comment Volume Dataset</u>	facebook_comment	1	40949	52
<u>Facebook metrics</u>	facebook_metrics	1	495	17
<u>Forest Fires</u>	forestfires	1	517	8
<u>Gas sensor array under dynamic gas mixtures</u>	ethylene_CO	1	4208261	17
<u>Gas sensor array under dynamic gas mixtures</u>	ethylene_methane	1	4178504	17
<u>Gas Turbine CO and NOx Emission Data Set</u>	gt_2011	2	7411	9
<u>Gas Turbine CO and NOx Emission Data Set</u>	gt_2012	2	7628	9
<u>Gas Turbine CO and NOx Emission Data Set</u>	gt_2013	2	7152	9
<u>Gas Turbine CO and NOx Emission Data Set</u>	gt_2014	2	7158	9
<u>Gas Turbine CO and NOx Emission Data Set</u>	gt_2015	2	7384	9
<u>Geographical Original of Music</u>	default_features	2	1059	68
<u>Geographical Original of Music</u>	default_chromatic	2	1059	116
<u>GPS Trajectories</u>	gps	1	163	3
<u>Greenhouse Gas Observing Network</u>	greenhouse	1	955167	14
<u>Individual household electric power consumption</u>	household	1	2049280	6
<u>ISTANBUL STOCK EXCHANGE</u>	akbilgic	1	536	8
<u>KEGG Metabolic Reaction Network (Undirected)</u>	RN_Undirected	1	64608	27
<u>KEGG Metabolic Relation Network (Directed)</u>	RN_Directed	1	53413	19
<u>Metro Interstate Traffic Volume</u>	metro	1	48204	4
<u>Online News Popularity</u>	OnlineNewsPopularity	1	39644	44
<u>Online Video Characteristics and Transcoding Time Dataset</u>	transcoding_mesurment	1	68784	6
<u>Optical Interconnection Network</u>	optical_interconnection	1	640	4
<u>Parkinson Speech Dataset with Multiple Types of Sound Recordings</u>	Parkinson_multiple	1	1040	26
<u>Parkinsons Telemonitoring</u>	parkinsons	2	5875	7
<u>Physicochemical Properties of Protein Tertiary Structure</u>	CASP	1	45730	9
<u>PM2.5 Data of Five Chinese Cities</u>	fivecities	1	49579	7
<u>Productivity Prediction of Garment Employees</u>	productivity	1	691	8
<u>QSAR aquatic toxicity</u>	qsar_aquatic_toxicity	1	546	8
<u>QSAR Bioconcentration classes dataset</u>	qsar_bioconcentration	1	779	9
<u>QSAR fish toxicity</u>	fish_toxicity	1	908	6
<u>Real estate valuation data set</u>	real_estate	1	414	5
<u>Real-time Election Results: Portugal 2019</u>	ElectionData	1	21643	7
<u>Relative location of CT slices on axial axis</u>	slice_localization	1	53500	373

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<u>Residential Building Data Set</u>	residential_building	2	372	7
<u>Seoul Bike Sharing Demand</u>	SeoulBike	1	760	9
<u>Servo</u>	servo	1	167	2
<u>SGEMM GPU kernel performance</u>	sgemm_product	1	241600	10
<u>SML2010</u>	sml1	1	2764	16
<u>SML2010</u>	sml2	1	1373	16
<u>Stock portfolio performance</u>	stock_portfolio	6	315	6
<u>Student Performance</u>	student_mat	1	395	13
<u>Student Performance</u>	student_por	1	649	13
<u>Superconductivity Data</u>	superconduct	1	21263	9
<u>UJIIndoorLoc</u>	UJIIndoorLoc	2	19937	125
<u>Wave Energy Converters</u>	WEC_Adelaide	1	71999	48
<u>Wave Energy Converters</u>	WEC_Perth	1	72000	48
<u>Wave Energy Converters</u>	WEC_Sydney	1	72000	48
<u>Wave Energy Converters</u>	WEC_Tasmania	1	72000	48
<u>Yacht Hydrodynamics</u>	yacht_hydrodynamics	1	308	6
<u>YearPredictionMSD</u>	YearPredictionMSD	1	515345	90